

On the Potential of Concurrency for Scaling W&C Applications in the ExaSCALE Era

Rupert Ford, STFC Ukri

Reinhard Budich, MPI-M

Julia Duras, DKRZ

Why this Presentation?

- ➔ Attempt in ESiWACE to tackle the topic „Concurrency“
- ➔ People had radiation and OBGC in mind
- ➔ More activity in that direction as well

- ➔ Somehow we got stuck: Why?
- ➔ Report* had to be written, the base for this talk

* Available on request from Reinhard

Concurrency: Which One?

- ➔ Rob Pike is a Canadian programmer and author: Go, Bell Labs, now at google.
- ➔ From Wikipedia:
„According to Rob Pike, concurrency is the composition of independently executing computations, [2] and concurrency is not parallelism:
 - ➔ **Concurrency** is about dealing with lots of things at once but **parallelism** is about doing lots of things at once.
 - ➔ **Concurrency** is about structure, **parallelism** is about execution,
 - ➔ Concurrency provides a way to structure a solution to solve a problem that may be (but is not necessarily) parallelizable.[3]“

(2) „Go Concurrency Patterns“. <https://talks.golang.org/2012/concurrency.slide#6> talks.golang.org. Retrieved 2021-04-08.

(3) "Go Concurrency Patterns". <https://talks.golang.org/2012/waza.slide#8> talks.golang.org. Retrieved 2021-04-08.

7th ENES HPC WS, 10.5.22, Corresponding Author: Reinhard Budich, MPI-M, reinhard.budich@mpimet.mpg.de

Concurrency: Which One?

➔ Definitions for C&W computing problems / type of concurrency

➔ a) ensembles / external

➔ b) model components / coupling

➔ c) comm. and comp. / I/O servers

➔ d) data structures / nodes or threads

➔ Here

➔ e) functions / intra-component ➔ **Functional Concurrency**

This Talk

- Intro
- Ansatz for a definition of functional concurrency
- Findings about experiences in the community
- The potential of functional concurrency
- Why it is so hard
- Potential Solutions & Outlook

Functional Concurrency: Ansatz for a Definition

➔ The report describes it as:

„Model components can often also be further split into finer-grain components with some of these components having the potential to run in parallel with each other. This intra-component functional parallelism is currently typically not exploited by model components ...“

➔ Examples include, but are not limited to

➔ atm - rad

➔ oce - obgc

➔ lnd - rivers

➔ ...

Findings about Experiences in the Community

→ Examples

→ MPAS

→ COSMO

→ LFRic

→ ICON

MPAS: Court

„soft“ factors, only estimates possible

MPAS Call Structure

Begin Timestep

contribution to the model time-step in realistic configurations

Radiation*

1. Integration Setup
2. Moist coefficients
3. Physics tendencies
4. Vertically implicit coefficients
5. Dynamic tendencies
6. Small step
7. Acoustic solver
8. Divergent damping
9. Large step
10. Scalars
11. Solve diagnostics
12. Substeps
13. Scalars
14. Velocity Reconstruction

End Timestep

CPU/GPU Switching

MPAS: Courtesy Rich Loft, Remarks

➔ Radiation

➔ To GPU

- ➔ Rad RRTMG was not yet ported to GPU, as it is now the case.
- ➔ Rad was 1/3 of the LoC of MPAS-A: Major task!
- ➔ Many lookup-tables problematic for memory access
- ➔ Not clear if spreading the task to many GPUs would scale and perform

➔ On CPU

- ➔ Would rad@cpu be fast enough for the rest? Also depending on ratio between
 - ➔ rad and dycore time step!
 - ➔ Performance of cpus and gpus

MPAS: Courtesy Rich Loft, Conclusions

➡ It depends ...

➡ Please refer to the report: Tremendous work!

➡ ... on implementation of the concurrency in the component(s)

COSMO - Preliminaries: Courtesy Carlos Osuna

- ➔ NWP code of MeteoSuisse parallelized with
 - ➔ OpenACC for Driver, parametrization, assimilation
 - ➔ GridTools for the dycore
- ➔ Observation
 - ➔ Strong scalability saturates at 40 k grid points per GPU device
 - ➔ GPUs can not be fully occupied, adding GPUs does not help
- ➔ Idea
 - ➔ Run dycore and rad (every 60th time-step) in parallel as GPU streams, OpenMP and OpenACC applied (async queues)
- ➔ Hypothesis
 - ➔ This way GPUs can be utilized in a way nearer to saturation

COSMO - Results: Courtesy Carlos Osuna

→ Results

- No bit-identical results, but differences should be small from theoretical considerations - full meteorological evaluation was not performed, though.
- Quote from report: „Even though we observed the desired task parallelism in the radiation scheme, we could not measure a significant improvement in performance corresponding to it.,,

→ Reasons

- (Too) Large kernels in the rad scheme use all resources, and block other kernels
- Controlling launch times for kernels would help here, but was not possible from OpenACC

→ My take

- Smart strategy, but disappointing results
- Strategy dropped for the time being
- Dependent on implementation of the concurrency in the component(s)

LFRic: Courtesy Rupert Ford

- ➔ W&C atmosphere code of MetOffice to come
 - ➔ Not yet complete, not yet with the desirable performance, but useable for prototypical case studies
 - ➔ Concurrency for components and data treated as usual, also with DSL (for functional and task low level concurrency on loop level)
- ➔ Approaches: High level concurrency
 - ➔ for slow physics, within a time-step
 - ➔ processes are independent of each other within a tilmestep
 - ➔ (Fast physics are not considered and executed sequentially)
 - ➔ for radiation, across time-step
 - ➔ Use physics consideration
 - ➔ Rad status is not (very) dependent on parameters in the same time-step, information can be used from earlier time-steps

LFRic, slow physics: Courtesy Rupert Ford

➔ Time-step in LFRIC as DAG:

➔ Add timing information, TS weighted

LFRic - Slow physics expanded: Courtesy Rupert Ford

LFRic slow physics

LFRic slow physics TS weighted

Different possibilities for concurrency under consideration, depending on complexity of components

Computation at rad time step !

LFRic, concurrent rad: Courtesy Rupert Ford

➔ Approach:

➔ Results:

➔ It depends

- ➔ on physical assumptions, and cost benefit considerations by scientists
- ➔ on the exact balance of costs for the different components, depending on their complexity and the frequency with which they are computed
- ➔ ... on the implementation of the concurrency in the component(s)

ICON: C. Many Iconists - Marco Giorgetta, Leonidas Linardakis, Julia Duras ...

- ➔ Complex coupled weather and climate model by DKRZ, DWD, KIT and MPI-M
 - ➔ Atm, Lnd, Oce
 - ➔ Provides ample concurrency in all dimensions
 - ➔ Coupling of the atmosphere and the ocean via the coupler library YAC
 - ➔ I/O-Server library CDI-PIO, enabling concurrent execution of I/O
 - ➔ Data parallelism within model components employing OpenMP and MPI
 - ➔ functional concurrency in ICON-A, ICON-O
- ➔ OBGC (HAMOCC)
 - ➔ provides a concurrent ocean case
 - ➔ Described elsewhere
 - ➔ It runs well (T. Ilyina, pers. comm.)
- ➔ Look at rad in ICON-A here

ICON-A: C. Many Iconists - Marco Giorgetta, Julia Duras ...

- ➔ Process splitting for slow physics in ICON-A (M. Giorgetta)
 - ➔ Coarse res / long time-steps can lead to higher tracer concentrations than the reference (neg. concentrations)
 - > physically not reasonable, numerically unstable
 - ➔ High res / short TS configurations allow to reduce number of processes (rad, diff, cloud μ -physics)
 - ➔ Sequential coupling currently
 - ➔ But considered for complete parallel coupling (some remarks next slide)
 - ➔ So far, partial parallel coupling was considered

Remarks on Complete Parallel Coupling in ICON-A

- ➔ Parallel coupling and computing of more than one "slow physics" process and dynamics not yet been done
 - ➔ It is a tremendous work, for which sustainability is not guaranteed
 - ➔ Parallel coupling scheme
 - ➔ Two synchronizations necessary:
 - ➔ Combine with some monitoring and regularization scheme to prevent rare exceptions
 - ➔ Scientifically parallel coupling scheme could be developed independently:
 - ➔ Once an accepted coupling scheme for a certain experiment is found, working with acceptable time steps (i.e. computing costs), such a parallel computing scheme could be developed and employed
 - ➔ Sustainability of the implementation questionable
 - ➔ With a completely parallelized computation of processes, distribution of resources to the tasks can be embedded in the model, invisible to the user
 - ➔ Dynamical process scheduling might be an option
- ➔ Distribute the common input state to all processes computed in parallel
 - ➔ Collect and process their output
 - ➔ Make input data and the tasks available within the same time step
 - ➔ Get work done as fast as possible
 - ➔ Collect results from all processes
 - ➔ Combining them ready for the next phase of computation

Partial parallel coupling in ICON-A

→ Concurrent computation of radiation process

→ Use of longer rad time-step:

$$\Delta t_{\text{rad}} = k \cdot \Delta t, k > 1$$

→ The larger k , the more the radiation will deviate from „true“ solution - affordable

→ Concurrent PSrad was developed

→ Own processes

→ different coupling scheme, different causality, different results

Sequential, „traditional“

Concurrent, PSrad_{conc}

Partial parallel coupling in ICON-A

→ Results:

- 25 quantities checked in 9 yr AMIP-like runs
- Deviation is in the range of a few percent
- Radiation accuracy can be increased by a reduced time-step length, without computational overhead
- Computational gain ok, though not terrific:
 - integration of the whole model gets faster by about the amount needed for the radiation computed sequentially
- Very much depending on resource distribution between $\rho\text{Srad}_{\text{conc}}$ and „rest of the model“
- Practical complications and intense testing necessary <- Very costly, **not affordable in our case!**
- And: ρSrad was dropped for other reasons

ICON: Conclusion

- ➔ ICON-A:
 - ➔ More work to be done
 - ➔ Re-structuring and -engineering in full swing (DestinE, Warmworld, others)
 - ➔ For functional concurrency, extra project funding applied for
- ➔ *Dependent on implementation of the concurrency in the component(s)*
- ➔ Seems to have worked for ICON-O/HAMOCC (OBGC)

The Potential of Functional Concurrency

- ➔ Dependent on implementation of the concurrency in the component(s)
- ➔ No generic approach visible, so case- and model-dependent
- ➔ AND: It is depending on intense scientific evaluation & cooperation
- ➔ But the only potential candidate for more parallelization
- ➔ Huge cost involved

Why it is so hard

- ➔ Radiation is special case since $\Delta t_{\text{rad}} \gg \Delta t_{\text{rest}}$ slow physics
- ➔ Other (sub-time-step) components need to be **modified scientifically** before they can be algorithmically and numerically altered in order to achieve concurrency ▀ **High effort, high risk**
- ➔ However, having the flexibility in the software to be able to test whether it is beneficial to run sub-components concurrently or not and being able to choose a different solution depending on the required configuration and underlying architecture is something that would be beneficial for scientists.
- ➔ In the report different scenarios concerning properties of the sub-components and the resource availability are discussed which would benefit from such flexibility
 - ➔ Flexibility in ordering of SC, or choosing different resolution, rates or precision might also help - discussed in the report
- ➔ Conclusion of this report: A well defined interface (of which a subroutine boundary with all data being passed by argument is considered sufficient) is necessary in order to be able to maintain a more flexibility for concurrency; two of four models have this already
- ➔ Depending on machine architecture, a mix of MPI&OpenMP&OpenACC seems most appropriate - also hard!
- ➔ Buffer space needs to be allocated to store information from former time steps, also depending on the scientific set-up
- ➔ Complexity seems to grow overwhelmingly

Why it is so hard

- ➔ Radiation is special case since $\Delta t_{\text{rad}} \gg \Delta t_{\text{rest}}$ slow physics
- ➔ Other (sub-time-step) components need to be **modified scientifically** before they can be algorithmically and numerically altered in order to achieve concurrency ▀ **High effort, high risk**
- ➔ However, having the flexibility in the software to be able to test whether it is beneficial to run sub-components concurrently or not and being able to choose a different solution depending on the required configuration and underlying architecture is something that would be beneficial for scientists.
- ➔ In the report different scenarios concerning properties of the sub-components and the resource availability are discussed which would benefit from such flexibility
 - ➔ Flexibility in ordering of SC, or choosing different resolution, rates or precision might also help - discussed in the report

- ➔ Conclusion of this report: A well defined interface (of which a subroutine boundary with all data being passed by argument is considered sufficient) is necessary in order to be able to maintain a more flexibility for concurrency; two of four models have this already
- ➔ Depending on machine architecture, a mix of MPI&OpenMP&OpenACC seems most appropriate - also hard!
- ➔ Buffer space needs to be allocated to store information from former time steps, also depending on the scientific set-up
- ➔ Complexity seems to grow overwhelmingly

Why it is so Hard Cont'd

- Radiation is special case since $\Delta t_{\text{rad}} \gg \Delta t_{\text{rest slow physics}}$
- Other (sub-time-step) components need to be modified scientifically before they can be algorithmically and numerically altered in order to achieve concurrency ▫ High effort, high risk
- However, having the flexibility in the software to be able to test whether it is beneficial to run sub-components concurrently or not and being able to choose a different solution depending on the required configuration and underlying architecture is something that would be beneficial for scientists.
- In the report different scenarios concerning properties of the sub-components and the resource availability are discussed which would benefit from such flexibility
 - Flexibility in ordering of SC, or choosing different resolution, rates or precision might also help - discussed in the report

- ➔ Conclusion of this report: A well defined interface (of which a subroutine boundary with all data being passed by argument is considered sufficient) is necessary in order to be able to maintain more flexibility for concurrency; two of four models have this already
- ➔ Depending on machine architecture, a mix of MPI&OpenMP&OpenACC seems most appropriate - also hard!
- ➔ Buffer space needs to be allocated to store information from former time steps, also depending on the scientific set-up
- ➔ Complexity seems to grow overwhelmingly

Potential Solutions

- ➔ Ideas/recommendations from the report for further investigation:
- ➔ Coupling systems and frameworks show potential
 - ➔ ESMF
 - ➔ DSL
 - ➔ Combination of library code, code-generation and -modification (CCPP@NCAR)
 - ➔ Lib between component and sub-component as a SC-wrapper

Outlook

- ➔ Technology changes
 - ➔ NVIDIA'S Multi-Instance GPU for better load balancing
- ➔ Further problems:
 - ➔ Proliferating programming codes
 - ➔ Heterogeneity
- ➔ Big projects plus pressure for more parallelism might help ...
- ➔ **We need to use the concept of functional concurrency to structure the problems in a way to parallelize execution of tailor-made codes of certain physical processes**

Thanks!

➔ Questions

ESiWACE2 has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823988